
FUNCTIONAL DEUTSCH UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

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Abstract: Let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m$ be Parseval p-frames for a finite dimensional Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then we show that

$$(1) \log(nm) \geq S_f(x) + S_g(x) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g,$$

where

$$\mathcal{X}_f := \{z \in \mathcal{X} : f_j(z) \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}, \quad \mathcal{X}_g := \{w \in \mathcal{X} : g_k(w) \neq 0, 1 \leq k \leq m\},$$

$$S_f(x) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p, \quad S_g(x) := - \sum_{k=1}^m \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_g.$$

We call Inequality (1) as **Functional Deutsch Uncertainty Principle**. For Hilbert spaces, we show that Inequality (1) reduces to the uncertainty principle obtained by Deutsch [*Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1983]. We also derive a dual of Inequality (1).

Keywords: Uncertainty Principle, Orthonormal Basis, Parseval Frame, Hilbert space, Banach space.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\widehat{\cdot}: \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$ be the unitary Fourier transform obtained by extending uniquely the bounded linear operator

$$\widehat{\cdot}: \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^d) \cap \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \ni f \mapsto \widehat{f} \in C_0(\mathbb{R}^d); \quad \widehat{f}: \mathbb{R}^d \ni \xi \mapsto \widehat{f}(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(x) e^{-2\pi i \langle x, \xi \rangle} dx \in \mathbb{C}.$$

The **Shannon entropy** at a function $f \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \setminus \{0\}$ is defined as

$$S(f) := - \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \left| \frac{f(x)}{\|f\|} \right|^2 \log \left| \frac{f(x)}{\|f\|} \right|^2 dx$$

(with the convention $0 \log 0 = 0$) [16]. In 1957, Hirschman proved the following result [10].

Theorem 1.1. [10] (*Hirschman Inequality*) For all $f \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \setminus \{0\}$,

$$(2) \quad S(f) + S(\widehat{f}) \geq 0.$$

In the same paper [10] Hirschman conjectured that Inequality (2) can be improved to

$$(3) \quad S(f) + S(\widehat{f}) \geq d(1 - \log 2), \quad f \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \setminus \{0\}.$$

Inequality (3) was proved independently in 1975 by Beckner [2] and Bialynicki-Birula and Mycielski [3].

Theorem 1.2. [2, 3] (*Hirschman-Beckner-Bialynicki-Birula-Mycielski Uncertainty Principle*) For all $f \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \setminus \{0\}$,

$$S(f) + S(\widehat{f}) \geq d(1 - \log 2).$$

Now one naturally asks whether there is a finite dimensional version of Shannon entropy and uncertainty principle. Let $\mathcal{H}$ be a finite dimensional Hilbert space. Given an orthonormal basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{H}$, the **(finite) Shannon entropy** at a point $h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau$ is defined as

$$S_\tau(h) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_j \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_j \right\rangle \right|^2 \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{H}_\tau := \{h \in \mathcal{H} : \langle h, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ [8]. In 1983, Deutsch derived following uncertainty principle for Shannon entropy which is fundamental to several developments in Mathematics and Physics [8].

Theorem 1.3. [8] (*Deutsch Uncertainty Principle*) Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then

$$(4) \quad 2 \log n \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}{2} \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau.$$

Recently, author derived Banach space versions of Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani uncertainty principle [13], Donoho-Stark approximate support uncertainty principle [12] and Ghobber-Jaming uncertainty principle [14]. We then naturally ask what is the Banach space version of Inequality (4)? In this paper, we are going to answer this question.

2. FUNCTIONAL DEUTSCH UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

In the paper, $\mathbb{K}$ denotes $\mathbb{C}$ or $\mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{X}$ denotes a finite dimensional Banach space over $\mathbb{K}$. Dual of $\mathcal{X}$ is denoted by $\mathcal{X}^*$. We need the notion of Parseval p-frames for Banach spaces.

Definition 2.1. [1, 6] Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a finite dimensional Banach space over $\mathbb{K}$. A collection $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ in $\mathcal{X}^*$ is said to be a **Parseval p-frame** ($1 \leq p < \infty$) for $\mathcal{X}$ if

$$(5) \quad \|x\|^p = \sum_{j=1}^n |f_j(x)|^p, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

Note that (5) says that $\|f_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$. Given a Parseval p -frame $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{X}$, we define the **(finite) p -Shannon entropy** at a point $x \in \mathcal{X}_f$ as

$$S_f(x) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_f := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : f_j(x) \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. Following is the fundamental result of this paper.

Theorem 2.2. (Functional Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) *Let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m$ be Parseval p -frames for a finite dimensional Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{(nm)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right)$$

and

(6)

$$\log(nm) \geq S_f(x) + S_g(x) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right) > 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g.$$

Proof. Let $z \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\|z\| = 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |f_j(z)|^p \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^m |g_k(z)|^p \right) = \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m |f_j(z)g_k(z)|^p \\ &\leq \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right)^p \\ &= \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right)^p mn \end{aligned}$$

which gives

$$\frac{1}{mn} \leq \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right)^p.$$

Since $1 = \sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, $1 = \sum_{k=1}^m \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$ and log function is concave, using Jensen's inequality (see [17]) we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_f(x) + S_g(x) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p} \right) + \sum_{k=1}^m \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p} \right) \\ &\leq \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \frac{1}{\left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p} \right) + \log \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \frac{1}{\left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p} \right) \\ &= \log n + \log m = \log(nm), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g. \end{aligned}$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_f(x) + S_g(x) &= - \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left[\log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p + \log \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \right] \\
&= - \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \\
&= -p \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right| \\
&\geq -p \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right) \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_k \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.3. *Theorem 1.3 follows from Theorem 2.2.*

Proof. Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Define

$$f_j : \mathcal{H} \ni h \mapsto \langle h, \tau_j \rangle \in \mathbb{K}; \quad g_j : \mathcal{H} \ni h \mapsto \langle h, \omega_j \rangle \in \mathbb{K}, \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Now by using Buzano inequality (see [4, 9]) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |f_j(h)g_k(h)| \right) &= \sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle h, \tau_j \rangle| |\langle h, \omega_k \rangle| \right) \\
&\leq \sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} \left(\|h\|^2 \frac{\|\tau_j\| \|\omega_k\| + |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}{2} \right) \right) \\
&= \frac{1 + \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.2 brings the following question.

Question 2.4. *Given p, m, n and a Banach space $\mathcal{X}$, for which pairs of Parseval p -frames $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m$ for $\mathcal{X}$, we have equality in Inequality (6)?*

Next we derive a dual inequality of (6). For this we need dual of Definition 2.1.

Definition 2.5. [5, 18, 19] *Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a finite dimensional Banach space over $\mathbb{K}$. A collection $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ in $\mathcal{X}$ is said to be a **Parseval p -frame** ($1 \leq p < \infty$) for $\mathcal{X}^*$ if*

$$(7) \quad \|f\|^p = \sum_{j=1}^n |f(\tau_j)|^p, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}^*.$$

Note that (7) says that

$$\|\tau_j\| = \sup_{f \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|f\|=1} |f(\tau_j)| \leq \sup_{f \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|f\|=1} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |f(\tau_j)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \sup_{f \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|f\|=1} \|f\| = 1, \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Given a Parseval p -frame $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{X}^*$, we define the **(finite) p -Shannon entropy** at a point $f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^*$ as

$$S_\tau(f) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_\tau^* := \{f \in \mathcal{X}^* : f(\tau_j) \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. We now have the following dual to Theorem 2.2.

Theorem 2.6. (Functional Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m$ be two Parseval p -frames for the dual $\mathcal{X}^*$ of a finite dimensional Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{(nm)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right)$$

and

(8)

$$\log(nm) \geq S_\tau(f) + S_\omega(f) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right) > 0, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*.$$

Proof. Let $h \in \mathcal{X}^*$ be such that $\|h\| = 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |h(\tau_j)|^p \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^m |h(\omega_k)|^p \right) = \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m |h(\tau_j)h(\omega_k)|^p \\ &\leq \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right)^p \\ &= \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right)^p mn \end{aligned}$$

which gives

$$\frac{1}{mn} \leq \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right)^p.$$

Since $1 = \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p$ for all $f \in \mathcal{X}^* \setminus \{0\}$, $1 = \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p$ for all $f \in \mathcal{X}^* \setminus \{0\}$ and log function is concave, using Jensen's inequality we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_\tau(f) + S_\omega(f) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p} \right) + \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p} \right) \\ &\leq \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \frac{1}{\left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p} \right) + \log \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \frac{1}{\left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p} \right) \\ &= \log n + \log m = \log(nm), \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*. \end{aligned}$$

Let $f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_\tau(f) + S_\omega(f) &= - \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left[\log \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p + \log \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \right] \\
&= - \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \\
&= -p \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right| \\
&\geq -p \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right) \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_k)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.6 again gives the following question.

Question 2.7. *Given p, m, n and a Banach space $\mathcal{X}$, for which pairs of Parseval p -frames $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m$ for $\mathcal{X}^*$, we have equality in Inequality (8)?*

Author is aware of the improvement of Theorem 1.3 by Maassen and Uffink [15] (cf. [7]) (motivated from a conjecture of Kraus [11]) but unable to derive Maassen-Uffink uncertainty principle from Theorem 2.2.

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